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Making the Invisible Visible for Off-Highway Machinery by Conveying Extended Reality Technologies

DELIVERABLE 6.2 – DEPLOYMENT, TESTING AND DEMONSTRATION OF THE THEIA-XR USE CASES (FIRST VERSION)

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Executive summary

The deployment, testing and demonstration activities on the first version of integrated THEIA^{XR} technologies and methodologies are described in this document. The validation and the results will be reported with D6.3.

At current development stage, for available technology out of WP3-5, feasible tests were executed to get first feedback. Technologies are first tested within the most promising use case and will later be tested on other use case. Some tests are performed in real- life setting and in demonstration environment for the use case application, others are performed with simulations.

Each use case chapter contains the relative testing activities with the already existing prototypes. Furthermore, a conclusion for the related testing activity and lessons learned is provided. Use case chapters conclude with the next steps. The conclusion at the end of the document provides a summary of the next actions within T6.2.

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1 Introduction

The purpose of task 6.2 is to deploy, test and demonstrate the methodologies, technologies, and use cases in demonstration settings. This entails conducting real-life tests for the three use cases, by incorporating actual snow groomer, port machine environment and excavation machinery into the testing procedures.

This deliverable D6.2 summarizes the deployment, testing, and demonstration activities performed on the first version of the implemented and integrated technologies and applications described in D6.1.

Learnings out of the testing and demonstration activities will be considered for the further development in WP3, WP4 and WP5.

The development and functional testing of technologies in the use cases, as presented here, consistently runs in parallel to concept co-design and validation activities within T3.2. All technologies described in the following chapters are incorporated in the vision scenarios (see D3.2) and will be further improved over time in accordance with operator feedback, but testing and validating their basic functionality is essential to ensure that the current concepts outlined in the vision scenarios are feasible in the first place. The tests and demonstrations discussed here have also served to support WP3 co-design activities and discussions, as will be briefly outlined in the “next steps” closing chapter of each use case.

Chapter 2-4 provides updates on the status of implementation, testing and demonstration related to the specific use case (snow grooming, logistics and construction) and describes the activities performed related to each use case.

The deliverable concludes in Chapter 5.

2 Use case 1 - Snow grooming

This section describes the specific activities performed related to the snow groomer use case. More precisely, we describe our real-world testing in Ridnaun (IT) in February of 2024. For this, the partners from TUG visited the partners from PRIN, to test their prototypes, developed in T5.1. The three prototypes, i.e. a panoramic thermal camera, a camera-laser system, and a camera-spotlight system, were mounted atop a snow-groomer to evaluate their performance in the harsh environment of a snow-groomer and find pitfalls, which may not be apparent when the devices are tested in a controlled, lab-environment.

2.1 Testing in real- life environment conditions at Ridnaun

The testing days at Ridnaun were performed on Monday 12th and on Tuesday 13th of February. In Table 1 and Table 2 the participants and actual conditions on the specific days can be found.

As one can see, conditions were great to test the prototypes, as we did not experience any precipitation.

Country: Italy	Test area: Ridnaun	Date: 12.02.2024
Participants: TUG (3), HAP (1), PRIN (3)		
Snow conditions: Flabby, soft	Weather condition: few clouds/ clear	Ambient temperature: between 0 and +4° C

Table 1: 1st test day at Ridnaun

Country: Italy	Test area: Ridnaun	Date: 13.02.2024
Participant(s): TUG (3), HAP (1), HdM (2), UL (1) PRIN (3)		
Snow conditions: Flabby, soft	Weather condition: few clouds/ clear	Ambient temperature: between 0 and +4° C

Table 2: 2nd test day at Ridnaun

2.1.1 Scope

The purpose of this test was to verify the three technology prototypes outlined in T5.1 by TUG under real-world conditions. Testing took place over two days. On the first day, we mounted the prototypes on the machine and set up communication between the devices, followed by initial test drives. On the second day, we conducted additional evaluations based on insights from the first day and performed further tests using a virtual 3D model of the Ridnaun area.

2.1.2 Preparation

Prior to the field test data has been shared between PRIN and TUG. A mesh of the summer terrain scan has been provided, as well as a target surface mesh (see Figure 1). Furthermore, the structural requirement like the weight and the packaging of each prototype technology have been shared. Both parties aligned on the electrical connection requirement. As the testing vehicle, the snow groomer *Prinoth Husky E-Motion* (a fully electric vehicle and the most sustainable snow groomer existing), has been chosen.

As preparation for the second test day a 3D representative of the area in Ridnaun was created during the day based onto the data collected the day before. The settings of the prototype technologies have been adjusted.

Figure 1: Mesh of summer terrain scan with target surface.

2.1.3 Assembly/ Calibration

The snow groomer (see Figure 2) was prepared at the Nordic slope in Ridnaun. The snow measurement system has been installed and calibrated. A special structure for the built-up has been prepared on the snow groomer. A brush guard support, which is available as optional for the *Husky E-Motion*, was selected to use as basis structure for the fixation. With small adaptations it was fixed onto the snow groomer we used. An additional wooden plate was assembled onto the structure to allow an easy fixation of the prototypes.

Since the prototypes need to be registered correctly in the reconstruction of the environment, we utilize the CAN bus information of the vehicle. For this, we implemented a simple Python Application Programming Interface (API) to access the GPS data of the snow groomer and provide localization within the virtual environment. To establish a connection and read out live data with this API, the CAN bus channel was prepared accordingly. Finally, the battery of the snow groomer was fully charged.

The partners from TUG arrived with their prototypes at 1 p.m. and immediately started to install their devices. This included the installation of modems and power cables. Furthermore, the calibration process began for each prototype technology (see Figure 2), which took some time.

Figure 2: Snow groomer at Nordic slope in Ridnaun and installation of the prototypes

2.1.4 Testing activities

After installation, we started at 5:30 p.m. with the first test drive, where we recorded data with the 360° thermal camera and tested the localization with the CAN bus API.

At 6 p.m. first tests with the spotlight have been performed. Initially, we tested the prototype on the vehicle while standing still, before we again drove a round on the test slope (see Figure 3).

Figure 3: Spotlight on snow surface during operation.

The field test with the laser projection started around 6:30 p.m. (see Figure 5). The static projection was tested to look at the area reach (see Figure 6). We projected different objects on the snow surface (see Figure 7) to evaluate the lasers brightness. Again, we performed tests during a test drive.

Figure 4: First laser projection onto snow

Figure 5: Full range laser projection on snow surface.

Figure 6: Specific laser projection on snow surface.

At 7:15 p.m. we concluded the testing day and the snow groomer returned to the parking area to charge there. Furthermore, we dismantled the panoramic thermal camera to protect it from the cold weather over night.

Tuesday 13.02.2024:

We arrived at the testing yield at 4:30 p.m. We immediately mounted the panoramic thermal camera and conducted a test drive with it. An example image form this panoramic thermal camera can be seen in Figure 7.

Figure 7: Example frame of the panoramic thermal camera mounted on the testing vehicle while driving down a slope in Ridnaun

Again, part of the test course driven to test the imaging capabilities of the thermal cameras and the localization accuracy of the GPS data with the CAN bus API.

At 6 p.m. the test with the spotlight has been performed. Initial tests with illuminating selected positions have been performed with the snow groomer standing still. Afterwards, a part of the slope has been driven with the prototype to test its functionality in real condition.

The field test with the laser projection started at around 6:30 p.m.

Here we tested the localization of the vehicle in the reconstruction to load the pre-defined primitives. For this, a seamless registration of the device in the reconstruction was necessary. The localized projection from within the vehicle can be seen in Figure 8.

Figure 8: An arrow projected on the snow surface with photographed from outside (left) and inside (right) the snow groomer.

At 7:30 p.m. we concluded the testing test drive finished, and the snow groomer returned to the parking area. All prototypes have been disassembled, repacked, and put back in the car from TUG.

2.2 Haptic device demonstration

On Tuesday 13th of February at Prinoth Headquarter in Sterzing a workshop was held to demonstrate the different possibilities offered by haptic feedback in the vehicle control interfaces. For that reason, a demonstrator from Haption was set up using a Haption Virtuose 6D coupled with a visualization demo with different exercises was prepared (see Figure 9). This setup allowed operators, managers and engineers to experience the feel of different force feedback schemes (virtual stiffness, damping, mass, collisions and guidance along trajectories) by playing through the exercises provided.

Figure 9: Haptic device demonstrator in action.

2.3 Ethical and privacy considerations extraction (demonstration)

The prototype for the workshop was developed and tested to elicit privacy-related and ethical concerns among snow groomer operators and other stakeholders (N = 6). The results demonstrated that the proposed structure of inquiry, incorporating both bottom-up (based on features from the extended TAM model) and top-down (based on features from the Schwartz Values Model [1][2]) approaches, is relevant to the end-user populations and provides the necessary information to inform further development of the technology in Value Sensitive Design [3] paradigm. Based on the results of the demonstrations, we implemented additional changes to the workshop structure in part dedicated to discussing technological ideas from the main co-design scenarios, namely adding features ranking procedure to the features analysis. We also identified the main values concerns for the use case: independence in actions, tangible control, and active mechanics to prevent overreliance on the developing features. These concerns motivate the next round of inquiry, which will include more developed features of the prototype.

2.4 Conclusion and lessons learned

In conclusion, the testing days at Ridnaun were successful in verifying the three technology prototypes from TUG in real conditions: a panoramic thermal camera, a camera-laser system, and a camera-spotlight system. The snow groomer used was prepared with a snow measurement system and a special structure for the installation of the prototypes. The prototypes arrived and were calibrated before. The testing activities for the prototypes were done in two consecutive days. Additionally, a workshop was held to demonstrate the different possibilities offered by haptic feedback in the vehicle control interfaces.

Lessons learned from this test include the importance of preparation, calibration, and installation of prototypes before testing activities. Additionally, the use of a 3D representative of the area in Ridnaun for testing purposes can be an effective tool in evaluating the functionality of prototypes in various conditions. Furthermore, privacy and ethical considerations must be taken into account during the development process of new technologies, as shown by the results of the demonstration of the haptic device. Overall, this test provided valuable insights for further development and improvement of these technology prototypes.

The haptics demonstrations and workshops in Sterzing allowed us to draw the following conclusions. First, haptics (and especially force feedback) is generally a rather obscure field for operators, which means operators vary wildly in their ability to imagine uses for haptics in their day-to-day operations. However hands-on testing and context presentations on the subject appear very beneficial in improving operator understanding of the technologies' potential. Second, operators were generally enthusiastic about the potential inclusion of haptics once they had gained a better feel for what these technologies enable. This goes towards validating the hypothesis underlying the project, according to which multimodal feedback could benefit operators. Finally, more specifically to the implementation of haptics in a vehicle cabin, it is apparent that operators need collocation of haptic feedback signals with the control elements the signals are associated with. For example, force feedback steering assistance and tactile warnings should be located within the steering elements, i.e. the track controls, while force feedback blade positioning assistance and tactile warnings should be located within the primary joystick.

CREA has tested the real time video pass through technology combined to virtual 3D scene in UNITY graphics using the Varjo XR headset (<https://varjo.com/>). The tested headset XR3 has very good video quality and the tracking works well. There are couple of different methods to define which areas of view are from the video pass through and what part is 3D graphics. The most suitable alternative, together with a cabin of the mobile machine, is to use a 3D mask. The area covered by the mask is drawn from the video stream. For the head tracking Varjo XR3 uses the base stations, which are also known as 'lighthouses' and tracks the exact location of headset by sweeping the room using wireless pulses and laser lines. In addition, the position of the mask relative to the head set needs to be known and this can be tracked by one or more QR tags. The Varjo SDK has support for QR tags but by default only one of the visible tags is used for positioning. To improve the mask positioning accuracy a solution was developed that multiple QR tags are used simultaneously, which was found to be a good improvement. Testing was done with a cabin CREA had and not yet with the snow groomer cabin. The wind screen of the snow groomer cabin is quite large, and it goes down almost to the floor level meaning the controls of the machine user interface are in front of the wind screen. This makes it more challenging to define a mask so that the interior of the cabin and all user interface controls are visible by the real time video stream. Utilizing depth information in addition to a mask could be a solution to the challenge.

2.5 Next steps

Due to the dependence on environmental conditions, the prototypes could not be tested in all potential situations. As especially the most critical conditions, like snowstorm and whiteout did not occur, additional testing days are required and will be planned accordingly.

Furthermore, it's planned to implement and test most promising concepts out of D3.2.

Regarding haptics components for UC1, the next steps will be to test and validate the concept for haptic snow groomer track controls (see Figure 10) prototyped based on operator feedback during the workshops in Sterzing. Similarly, the 6-DoF haptic device integrating the snow groomer joystick handle will need to be tested to validate ergonomics and the control and feedback functions proposed in deliverable D4.4. The designs of both devices are described in more detail in deliverable D5.5.

Figure 10: First prototype of haptic track controls featuring independent force and vibrotactile feedback on each of the levers.

The overall visualization infrastructure and interaction system is the controlling system that will connect all solutions together and enables the handling of the available data inside the cabin. Currently, the system is still under development and first integration steps with individual technology providers is currently taking place. No demonstration activities have been performed yet and are planned according to the technologies to be integrated in the use case demonstrator.

Regarding the snow groomer simulation, the next steps will be to further develop especially the dynamic physics simulation of the snow groomer functions to be able to provide good virtual measurement information, which can be utilized for the haptic feedback. Also, the state of the snow groomer model will be made available as IO channels which can be further routed to CAN messages in a hardware in the loop (HiL) testing environment.

Impressions from the tests and demonstrations have been gathered by HdM and presented to vehicle operators from all use cases at various points during WP3 co-design activities to illustrate the project progress and specific technology concepts. For example, impressions of the laser projection, spotlight and thermal camera functionality, which were tested and demonstrated in Ridnaun, have served to visualize and discuss these features in co-design workshops with vehicle operators across all use cases. In the case of laser projections, this has raised questions regarding the safety and applicability of this technology, e.g., on construction sites (other workers and people in the area may be blinded, ground projections may not be visible in bright sunlight, etc.), or even in UC1 in fog and other bad weather conditions (can laser projections help with navigation during white-out scenario?). More testing will be required to clarify these questions.

3 Use case 2 – Logistics

This section is focusing on a logistic use case (UC2) and it is reporting three development cycle, each yielding functional prototypes evaluated by KALMAR personnel. Work has been done in close co-operation with WP3 and more detailed description of prototypes could be found in “D3.4 – Low-Fidelity XR Prototypes (First Version)”. Here is list of each evaluation and demonstration sessions:

1. The first prototype on May 16, 2023 in VTT’s XR laboratory
2. The second prototype on November 30, 2023 in VTT’s XR laboratory
3. The third prototype on February 27, 2024 in VTT’s XR laboratory

3.1 The first prototype

The initial prototype was built using Unity 2022.3.2f1 LTS, an upgrade from Unity 2021 LTS. While transitioning to the new version, no significant alterations or additions were observed. In addition to Unity’s native packages, third-party packages were incorporated to enrich interaction with specific hardware. Notably, Varjo’s SDK for Unity (version 3.4.0) is integrated with the Varjo XR-3 headset to facilitate mixed-reality functionalities. This integration enables the headset to display footage captured by its front cameras within the virtual environment, such as showcasing real steering wheels and joysticks for user interaction, as seen in the operation of the reach stacker. Furthermore, Ultraleap’s SDK (version 6.8.1) is utilized for tracking hand movements and gestures, facilitating user interaction with virtual menus.

To develop and run the application on the Vario XR-3, a high-end PC is required. The main specifications of the PC that was used are the following:

- OS: Windows 10 Pro
- CPU: Intel Core i9-10900KF @ 3.70GHz, 10 Cores, 20 Logical Cores
- RAM: 64GB @ 3200MHz
- GPU: NVIDIA GeForce RTX 3090 48GB VRAM

3.1.1 Visualization

The application can be run only on a normal monitor showing a digital twin of a harbour which a reach stacker and a container to grab. At any moment, the user can wear the Varjo XR-3 HMD to enter the virtual scene in first person, while still being able to see the real monitor and the physical devices used to control the vehicle thanks to Mixed Reality features (see Figure 11).

Figure 11: The user can wear the HMD at any time. In the virtual scene, physical devices such as the monitor and the joystick are still visible.

Displayed on the monitor are three camera views: (i) a perspective camera facing the vehicle's forward direction, occupying the majority of the screen to provide a broad overview akin to on-site operator

perspective; (ii) an orthographic camera focused on the left side of the spreader; (iii) another orthographic camera directed downwards toward the spreader and the ground. The primary camera offers a general view, while the orthographic cameras aid in precise situations, presenting a 2D projection of the scene devoid of perspective distortions, exclusive to the virtual realm, showcasing a key advantage of digital twins over physical camera footage.

To assist with precise placement, lines connecting each twist lock to its designated corner casting are drawn, displaying the distance between them in meters. In response to feedback from pilot testing, where users found the distance lines insufficient, three-dimensional arrows are now rendered atop each twist lock. These arrows, color-coded for clarity, turn red when distant from their target and green when in close proximity, pointing towards their respective corner castings similar to compass needles. As the twist lock approaches its target, the arrow aligns vertically downwards for enhanced guidance. See Figure 12.

Figure 12: The white arrow is visible until the vehicle points in the right direction. Then, four arrows appear on top of the twist locks to align them to the container.

3.1.2 Interactions

The operator controls the reach stacker with a Logitech G29 steering wheel and a Logitech Extreme 3D joystick, and virtual environment with hand gestures (see Figure 13).

Physical devices are used to give commands to real-world objects. The Extreme 3D is mapped the same way as the joystick inside a real reach stacker and is used to control the boom and spreader. The G29 allows to steer and drive, with the pedals mapped to throttle, brake and reverse throttle. Hand-tracking is used to adjust the scene visualization, for example, moving the user's position inside the virtual scene or binding their movement to the vehicle when driving.

Figure 13: Setup of the first prototype. From the left, there are the Varjo XR-3, Logitech G29 steering wheel and pedals, and Logitech Extreme 3D.

The separation between physical and virtual input is meant for the user to avoid making slips and unintentionally operating machinery instead of moving their position in the virtual scene. Moreover, physical controllers can provide more precise input than hand-tracked gestures, and they better resemble the real-life experience of operating a reach stacker, thus easing the shift from the traditional control system to a remote-control scenario.

3.1.3 Hand tracking

In the realm of Mixed Reality interactions, the decision centered on using either physical VR controllers or hand tracking. Both systems offer similar interactions, with nuanced differences. VR controllers, in an outside-in tracked setup, track movements beyond the HMD's field of view, providing precise movement tracking. Hand tracking, conversely, offers immediate use and seamless transition from physical devices to virtual menus. Opting for hand tracking was logical due to its convenience and absence of additional equipment. However, Varjo XR-3's hand tracking, though initially promising, required more user training than anticipated to ensure consistent hand visibility during gestures. To streamline interactions, two virtual menus—"rotation" and "movement"—were introduced, activated by displaying the left hand's palm to the HMD's cameras. Originally, the menus were anchored to the hand's position, causing difficulty in accuracy due to hand movement. To address this, the menus were redesigned to anchor to a virtual cube, inspired by Ultraleap's hand-tracking technology. Users activate the menus by displaying the left-hand palm, which triggers the appearance of virtual cubes. Selection is made by pinch or grab gestures, allowing free movement within the environment. Upon release, the assigned menu appears relative to the cube's position, remaining fixed until the cube is returned to its anchor position beside the left hand's palm (see Figure 14). Users can interact with the rotation menu by grabbing the sphere and moving it around the cube, while the movement menu provides three clickable buttons and three sliders that can be pressed and dragged.

Figure 14: Rotation menu (left) and movement menu (right).

3.1.4 Video of the first prototype

The video of the first prototype could be found in here:

<https://youtu.be/5oo0P3goICl?si=yDxoZuqvJMhQQkog>

Figure 15: Screenshot out of the first prototype video.

3.2 The second prototype

Users identified several limitations when using an HMD in the initial prototype. Consequently, the subsequent version was tailored for display on VTT's powerwall and a 60-inch 4K Samsung display.

3.2.1 Visualization

In visualization the significant departure from the first iteration is the fundamental technological approach. Rather than constructing a digital twin of the reach stacker and its environment, the system enables operators to observe the scene via strategically positioned 360° cameras. These cameras are strategically located on the reach stacker and in key areas of the surrounding environment, including atop poles or, ideally, on manoeuvrable drones capable of providing desired angles on demand.

The AR guidance system (**Error! Reference source not found.**7) consists of the following elements:

- Highlights: pick-up location, placement location, container corners, vehicle path; (see Figure 16 (a), (b), (c))
- Vehicle: centre line, tipping axis, load chart, counterweight safety area; (see Figure 16 (d), (e), (f), (g))
- Container: top face - corner castings and twist locks positions; front face - total weight, centre of mass line; ground projection - weight and percentage at the corners, centre of mass point; (see Figure 16 (c), (d), (f), (g))
- Obstacles: people tracking. (see Figure 16 (e))

Figure 16: AR guidance system elements.

The system's UI employs five distinct colours to convey various types of information: (i) amber for screen-space UI elements; (ii) blue to highlight containers; (iii) green to indicate safe operating conditions; (iv) yellow to denote potential hazards; and (v) red to signify imminent danger.

Interactive elements within the guidance system utilize green, yellow, or red exclusively. These elements dynamically adjust their colour based on operator actions or environmental conditions. For instance, the container's centre of mass transitions from red to yellow and finally to green as it moves closer to the vehicle's centre line. Conversely, tracking boxes around individuals near the vehicle shift from red, indicating imminent danger, to yellow and green as the distance increases, ensuring safety awareness.

3.2.1.1 Sound

In the second prototype application, the sound system includes background noise typical of a harbour environment, such as the constant sound of sea waves crashing against the pier, strong wind noise, and seagull cries. Additionally, the vehicle's engine emits sound that varies according to its speed or load, while emitting a distinct low-frequency beep when reversing to alert harbour personnel.

Furthermore, the obstacle tracking system emits a high-frequency beeping sound, distinguishable from the vehicle's reversing sound. The frequency and intervals of the beeping correspond to the distance to the obstacle, decreasing as the obstacle approaches. When an obstacle enters a zone of imminent danger, the beeping shifts to a constant high-frequency tone to alert the operator.

3.2.1.2 Interactions

The Logitech Extreme 3D joystick is mapped the same way as the joystick inside a real reach stacker and it is used to control the boom and spreader. No interactions were designed for driving, as the vehicle is assumed to go to the designated location on its autonomously.

Figure 17: Camera system's preview images and their docking positions.

The camera system (see Figure 17) offers operators flexibility in customizing screen space by rearranging smaller preview images for each streaming camera with the mouse pointer. Previews can be dragged and dropped anywhere on the screen, with predefined docking positions available. Double-clicking a preview image switches the main camera view, while holding the right mouse button enables changing camera direction by dragging the pointer. Zoom level adjustment is achieved by scrolling the mouse wheel, and pressing the middle mouse button resets the camera.

Keyboard shortcuts facilitate changing the main camera view, and an emergency stop feature halts the vehicle with the "Space" key. Moreover, hand-tracking interactions provide an alternative to mouse interactions. Using gestures performed by the left hand, operators can rotate the camera and switch to full-screen views with ease.

3.2.2 Video of the second prototype

The video of the second prototype could be found in here:

https://youtu.be/Xu8Qz2fv47A?si=4LGu8Atm_7UKkc07

Figure 18: Screenshot out of the second prototype video

3.3 The third prototype

The third prototype builds upon the second iteration, incorporating minor updates such as weather condition integration, color-coded distance lines, and a Lidar view. These enhancements aim to enhance the user experience, addressing feedback highlighted during the review of the second prototype. The primary addition is the implementation of haptic feedback for reachstacker pick and place control.

3.3.1 Visualization

3.3.1.1 Color-coded distance lines

We introduced color-coded distance lines that connected the container's casting corners to the reachstacker's twist locks to provide visual hints even in the front camera (the previous hints were only visible from the spreader camera) as could be seen in Figure 19. This feature was motivated by the fact that especially experienced drivers tend to rely mostly on the front camera, and they were thus missing a lot of the AR information that was more visible on other cameras. Traditional traffic lights were added to the spreader, as well as spreader width presents for each container size (for 20, 30, and 40 ft containers).

Figure 19: Color-coded distance lines.

3.3.1.2 Lidar view

The application display includes a simulated "LiDAR view" (see Figure 20), merging a virtual representation of the reachstacker's spreader (from the vehicle's IMU) with a container point cloud (from a LiDAR scanner on the boom). This view complements camera sensors, especially in limited visibility scenarios, like placing containers on tall stacks. By creating a 3D digital twin of the scene, it addresses issues with 2D imagery.

The simulation's balance between quality and performance, determined in user testing, involves casting 10,000 rays towards a container corner with a 30° angle for both azimuth and zenith. A virtual LiDAR sensor on the boom's lower face provides this data, offering a feasible real-world implementation. The reachstacker's spreader is visible thanks to the vehicle's IMU data, while the container becomes visible thanks to the lidar points captured by the lidar sensor.

Figure 20: Screenshot of the Lidar view feature.

3.3.1.3 Hand tracking feedback

When the operator uses any of the hand-tracking features, they are made aware of the input the application is receiving, and how it is responding to that thanks to an "hand tracking feedback" widget (see Figure 21). A small sphere represents the hand position relative to the hand-tracking device. If the sphere is orange, it means that no hand is being tracked. If the sphere is yellow, it means that the hand is tracked but it is outside

of the allowed interaction area (visualized as a transparent dome). Finally, when the sphere is green it means that the hand is being tracked and the operator can perform gestures.

Figure 21: Screenshot of the hand tracking feedback feature. The sphere is currently orange because no hands are being tracked.

3.3.1.4 Camera system

The camera system in the third prototype underwent modifications to enhance workspace flexibility. Now, each camera preview window can expand and resize, occupying up to one-third of the powerwall screen. This allows users to customize camera combinations for their tasks. Each expanded camera view includes an adjustable field of view slider. Furthermore, camera view direction can be controlled not only from the main powerwall view but also from any window associated with that camera, be it a preview or expanded view.

3.3.1.5 Weather system

The third prototype includes a weather system, which is implemented as a set of switchable presets. Currently, there are two weather system presets: *Rain* (Figure 22, left), and *Snow* (Figure 22, right).

Figure 22: Left: rain weather preset; right: snow weather preset.

3.3.2 Haptics

In the third prototype, Haption contributed by integrating their Virtuose 6D device. The device acted as a stand-in for the force-feedback enabled joystick in development by Haption for the THEIA^{XR} project (see deliverable D5.5 for details), and directly interfaced with the virtual reachstacker's control system. Specifically, the choice was made to lock all degrees of freedom except rotations around the x and y axes of the handle base, to replicate existing reachstacker joystick kinematics while being able to provide additional force feedback cues along those axes. The x axis controlled boom extension, and the y axis controlled boom rotation (see Figure 23). Additional concepts for haptic feedback are detailed in deliverable D4.4.

Figure 23: By blocking the translation of its handle and only allowing 2 degrees of rotation, the Virtuose's handle emulates a traditional analog stick, while still being able to provide force feedback.

3.3.3 Video of the third prototype

The video of the third prototype could be found in here:

<https://youtu.be/gfgrw0SgZeM?si=YW029iBuQ8YNH6c0>

Figure 24: Screenshot out of the third prototype video

3.4 Reachstacker modelling

The target is to modify a reachstacker model for VTT's virtual environment. The machine's features were modified to match with the demonstration machine (like sensor inputs, driving and braking behaviours were updated).

We tested also developed model with our own simulator platform. The system is really compact and does not require a specific large room with wide doors, etc. The platform can be utilized for training of operators in the cabin and when they are remote-controlling the machine. We are also pre-testing some new features of the machine with the simulator environment, before we utilize it for example to HIL testing. New safety features for remote control have been tested with simulator and demonstrator for bigger audience.

Figure 25: Portable simulation setup for reachstacker

3.5 360° Camera Testing and 3D Audio Testing

Kalmar has tested Nokia RXRM video management platform for teleoperation at test yard in Tampere, Finland. Nokia RXRM is designed for 360° video transmission over wireless networks. The platform is also supporting 2D cameras and it is possible to combine many streams as one combined stream (collage). Same platform is also supporting 3D audio signals which were also tested at the test yard.

In the system, onboard cameras were connected to onboard video server computer (laptop). Ethernet was used to streaming video from cameras to a video server which was on a separate network for this purpose. Different operators' views were created in the onboard video server. A client computer on the infrastructure opened the connection to the onboard video server. Maximum bandwidth utilized can be limited to optimize the wireless communication. Information can be added as overlay to the video screen. It was possible to switch the views from the client computer.

Figure 26: Client video screen example

Figure 27: Architecture of the RXRM system

Cameras were installed to the high pole in order to vibration damping features of the cameras and was working well. It was easy to have a good quality view on VR glasses. Audio features were also tested with VR glass integrated headphones. Audio was really realistic and the operator could hear from which direction the sound was coming.

Next we are trying to find the optimal static latency for minimizing the jitter of the videos. A constant small “heartbeat” animation for indicating the actual connection state of the video stream will be added. In the next version, live machine overlay data will be sent from a MQTT broker.

3.6 5G SA Mobile Network Testing

A new data collection unit was set up for being able to see what happens in the mobile network. It consists of a managed switch with mirror/monitoring ports and a small computer with direct access to Eth0- The Eth1 port was connected to the monitoring port. With Eth0 access, the data collection is possible to start at any moment remotely. With this setup, it was easy to monitor different tested scenarios.

Initial 5G onboard test was performed with one 5G router connected to WAN out port on the onboard XC216 switch. To support the possible need for video streams at Sweden, the test communication system was updated. 5G was left for automation communication only, connected to WAN out on XC216 with no MTU restrictions. Existing standard WLAN was connected directly to onboard IPC port for all other communications video streams, remote controls and other NATted communication. This setup will be used also in the final demonstration, the only difference is that the 5G communication will be sliced from the public network.

Figure 28: 5G + WiFi setup at Tampere Finland

3.7 Changed Needed to the Demonstration Machine

We had to make some modifications to our test machine in Sweden, because requirements are different in teleoperated machine compared to remote controlled machine (controller can see the machine and standing nearby). The machine was a remote controlled version.

We had to select new brake by wire valve for the machine to guarantee the safety of the machine. At the same time, we decided to add more E-stop buttons to the machine. We designed the brackets for the new sensors of the machines (3 x 360° cameras, microphone and lasers for obstacle detection). We had to find also good places for Wi-Fi and 5G antennas. The boom is blocking the signals in low position if the antennas are on top of the cabin. We designed brackets for the boom (lower end of the boom). We had to also make SW changes to the automation layer of our onboard computer to take care of made changes (safety and new functionalities).

Figure 29: Control system layout of the reachstacker

3.8 Conclusion and lessons learned

The integration of XR environments with human-centered evaluation and design methods has shown great promise for early-stage UX design. Over three development cycles, test users provided valuable feedback on

innovative approaches for the remote operation concept, although challenges remain, such as the learning curve associated with XR UI elements, particularly with gesture-based interactions. By the end of the second XR prototype iteration, however, the system was deemed highly suitable for the remote operation of a harbor reach stacker.

The haptics tests and developments in the third prototype allowed us to draw two main conclusions. First, force feedback schemes which cause the operator to “fight” the interface to maintain control over the container are not suitable. These include for example, the direct application of force or torque to the joystick handle which is proportional to container weight, pulling the joystick towards a different pose than that desired by the operator. Instead, it is much more relevant to provide this haptic information in the form of resistance to motion, by implementing virtual friction and viscosity proportional to container weight. Second, operators validated the potential usefulness of collision force feedback (tested with feedback of collisions between the container and the ground). However, they also noted that maybe tactile feedback could be sufficient for this, or could serve as a complementary means of feedback for finely detecting collisions.

In the next development cycle, the most effective features identified during the three iterations will be implemented into the actual remote operation station and we have to implement needed changes to the machine itself and test the whole system together with wireless connection. This will include further refining the XR interface and interaction methods to enhance usability and address the learning curve for novel XR UI elements. Continuous user involvement and iterative design will be essential to ensure the station meets user needs effectively. Next steps will be do in close co-operation with task T3.4.

3.9 Next steps

In the next phase of development, the most suitable features identified through the three iteration cycles will be carefully selected and implemented into the actual remote operation station. This phase will involve further refinement of the XR interface and interaction methods based on user feedback. Additionally, efforts will be made to streamline the learning curve associated with novel XR UI elements to enhance usability and user acceptance.

Component will be installed to the machine and SW changes will be tested first in HIL environment and then with real machine. We need to modify our existing remote control desk so that we can install new components to it. We have to also make changes to remote control desk software because of new UX components and changes in machine side. The communication from Finland to Sweden must be tested based on our experiences on test yard. Wi-Fi will be utilized for video streams, because we don't have private network in Sweden yet. Test yard in Sweden is feasible for this kind of testing, but we still need some trailer models for the test yard.

As in the previous use case, impressions from the tests and demonstrations have been gathered by HdM and presented to vehicle operators mainly in UC2 (due to this being the only explicit remote-control scenario) at various points during WP3 co-design activities to illustrate the project progress and specific technology concepts. For example, impressions of the XR navigation indicators and twist-lock positioning indicators have served to visualize and discuss these features in co-design workshops with vehicle operators from Hanko port in UC2. Upcoming UC2 co-design workshops will focus on the visual presentation of these features and information requirements of the operators to help improve upon the current status of developments.

4 Use case 3 – Construction

Based on the preliminary extend of the interaction concept for use case 3 (see Deliverable D3.2) this section reports on the progress of realization and testing by means of interactive prototypes. Two platforms were used for this – a CASE-WX185 excavator and a cabin mock-up.

4.1 Testing at the Excavator-Demonstrator

4.1.1 Hardware- setup

A CASE-WX185 excavator from the chair of construction machinery, TU Dresden, was equipped with sensor- and human-machine-interface-devices according to the scenario description of use-case 3.

Scenario 1, “Finish Grading”, features a novel LED-Matrix display on the bottom of the excavator’s arm. The display consists of a 16x16 rgb-LED-panel which indicates information for the operator close to the area of operation. The matrix-display is used to visualize and animate bitmaps to provide helpful information about the derivation to the target-height or warning indicators. The same information is depicted on the main display inside the cabin which shows the digital twin of the excavator and the target design model. Besides the real-time geometry visualization, a surface mesh of the actual environment is visualized based on the LIDAR-data. Two vertical bar-indicators highlight the derivation between actual bucket height and target height as in a state-of-the-art machine-control-system.

Scenario2, “Collision Avoidance”, relies mainly on camera-based person detection setup. Three cameras on the left, right and rear of the machine monitor the blind spots of the operator. An AI-based person-detection software detects persons in the collision area and warns the operator. The main-HMI is an LED-stripe around the front facing window that encodes distance and direction of the detected persons with position, colour and size of enlightened LED segments.

Scenario 3, “Infield Design” is mainly based on the big display in the cabin to visualize target models to the operator. The design outline is loaded to the main-controller and can be displayed in relation to the measured surface of the surroundings.

4.1.2 Testing the 3d-machine-control-system on the initial prototype

Several test runs have been taken out for the initial hardware-setup including the matrix-display and the main-display mainly covering the scenario 1 of the construction use-case. In three events, the HMI-setup was evaluated by

- technicians and engineers of the chair of construction machinery,
- the THEIA^{XR} Consortium during the consortium meeting in Dresden (see Figure 26)
- experts from the construction machine industry

Figure 30: Impressions from the initial tests.

During the testing, each participant had the opportunity to operate the excavator. The participants familiarized with the operation of the machine and performed a task of finish grading in the centre plane of the machine. Understanding the operation with the joysticks and simultaneously looking at the bucket and on the 3d-machine-control system was confirmed as a cognitive challenge. The LED-matrix display above the bucket was considered a helpful assistance system to produce a satisfying grading.

The tests were performed both in bright daylight and during night.

4.1.3 Testing the collision warning system

First tests of the person detection system and light indicators on the front window have been taken out to prove technical functionality and to assess the expectations and the intuitive understanding of the HMI by the participants. The participants could try out the system by walking around the excavator or let people walk around the excavator while they watch the HMI inside the cabin (see Figure 27). As already identified in the HMI-lab tests of the front-window-light-system, the intuitive understanding of the light indicators and the encoded information is different among the participants. Further tests will target the understanding and handling of this novel HMI-approach.

Figure 31: Testing of camera-based person detection system for the collision warning system.

4.2 Testing at the HMI-Lab-demonstrator

4.2.1 Hardware- setup

For exploration, prototyping and evaluation a multimodal cabin mock-up as part of a technical physical-digital interaction framework was used. The cabin mock-up consists of an excavator seat, an adjustable cabin frame made of aluminium profiles, two modular armrests, projection wall as well as mounts and tripods to position further equipment and devices (see Figure 28).

The digital part of this platform is capable to link various data streams from an application simulation, physical and digital control elements and information presentation devices to prototype interactive behaviour of machine user interfaces.

To prototype various conceptual XR interaction features this setup is equipped with three 14" touch displays (consumer-grade tablets), a 5" smartphone on the armrest to mimic a mini-display, various physical control elements (e.g. industrial-grade joysticks, rotary pushbuttons, buttons, sliders, touch panels, steering wheel and pedals) including two machine-grade joysticks, a touchpad, a leap motion and an Intel RealSense depth camera for body and gesture tracking, light and laser projectors covering the armrest, the a-pillars, the projection wall and the floor around the cabin, a light feedback system, vibration modules for implementation in physical controls and wearable devices as well as an 5.1 audio system for acoustic feedback in the cabin.

The software TouchDesigner is used as the primary data hub for data processing, modulation and conversion to connect all digital components. The software ProtoPie is used to prototype graphical user interfaces to be displayed through touch displays and projections. This platform allows medium-fidelity prototypes to be used at an early stage with little installation effort, thus providing the necessary flexibility for exploring and testing different solution approaches.

Figure 32: Hardware setup of the HMI Lab demonstrator.

4.2.2 Realizing and testing the ambient light feedback modality

The ambient light feedback system was also implemented and tested in the cabin mock up with different XR functional mappings such as proximity object warnings, tool position indicators and sub-surface object warnings. The light feedback system was integrated with modular light strips that were arranged in different configuration to test for good visibility and spatial resolution to e.g. map objects in the environment. Several arrangements around the windscreen and a terminal display mounted to the a-pillar were tested (see Figure 29). Display-attached light system using just a single strip and using two parallel strips have been put in place exploring the capabilities of such a system. Furthermore, different spatial configurations were realized to investigate visibility during work tasks. The “small o” shape, that split the windscreen was preferred. To mimic the real behaviour of an object-indicating light feedback, an artificial environment with placeable objects was created in TouchDesigner that rendered signals for the LED strips (see Figure 30). This allowed to create and move virtual objects that resemble as spatial light feedback with the “o”-shape representing a full 360° cover of the cabins surrounding. This setup was used for a first expert evaluation with a colleague with decent machine operation experience. The setup was and is also used to experiment with signal designs (animations, colour and parameter mappings), as well as utilizing this interaction technique for other feedback systems (e.g. warnings, and the 3d-machine-control-system). Currently, this setup is about to be extended with a synchronized virtual machine and environment simulation to further increase immersion for evaluation purposes.

Lichtring um Display

1-facher LED-Ring

- geschlossener Ring mit einem LED-Streifen
- kann an einer Position nur eine Farbe/Animation darstellen
- an einer Stelle der LED-Rings kann nur eine Information dargestellt werden

2-facher LED-Ring

- geschlossener Ring mit zwei LED-Streifen
- kann an einer Position zwei Farben/Animationen nebeneinander darstellen
- Möglichkeit, mind. zwei Informationen an einer Stelle des LED-Rings darzustellen
 - zwei Objekte an (nahezu) der gleichen Stelle
 - ein Objekt plus eine zusätzliche Information zu diesem Objekt
 - ein Objekt und eine Meldung/Warnung eines anderen integrierten Assistenzsystems

Lichtring um/an Frontscheibe

LED um gesamte Frontscheibe

LED um oberen Teil der Frontscheibe

LED an unteren Teil der oberen Scheibe

LED links/rechts an Frontscheibe

LED auf Trennkante der Frontscheibe

LED um unteren Teil der Frontscheibe

Figure 33: Conceptual Variations of the light feedback system that were iterated in the Lab demonstrator.

Figure 34: The final configuration of the Light-feedback system in the Lab demonstrator

4.2.3 Realizing and testing the digital mirror feature

The second feature we realized in the cabin mock-up was a digital mirror display. The idea was to extend the operator view through providing an extended visual projection of the surrounding focusing the whole area on the sides and behind the machine. In a first version a white board at the upper end of the windscreen was used for a video projection that showed a scripted video of a construction site. This first version already implemented a highlighted pedestrian that passed by which was accompanied by a red light dot on a light strip that was attached underneath the projection area (see Figure 31). For a second version we plan to extend the field of view through warping the camera perspective. Also advanced means of video augmentation will be implemented providing additional information regarding the detected object. The camera stream will also be connected to a dynamic environment simulation that react to joystick movements on the physical armrest. It is also planned to implement means of interactivity so the operator can manipulate characteristics of the visualization such as camera angle zoom and type and style of augmented information.

Figure 35: The screen projection system of the Lab demonstrator. On the left it is a test setup that shows the capabilities of multi-screen projection. The picture on the right shows the first version of a digital back mirror.

4.2.4 Realizing the ground projection feature

The third feature that was already realized was the ground projection of simple graphical indicators to test this feedback modality regarding its utilization to communicate ground levels, level deviations, planned geometries or hidden objects. Two setups in combination with the cabin mock-up were tested so far – a regular beamer and a laser projector. In a first test, simple dot animations were used to elaborate on graphical style (grid, lines, colour map), colours and size, resulting in a preference for a dot grid with small objects (see Figure 32). A second version implemented an adjustable visualization with TouchDesigner that allows to change mapping method, grid and object size. This visualization was also fed with 3D data from the Intel RealSense depth camera to create a 3d object mapping that highlighted height differences through colour. We are currently working in advancing the range of graphical styles, projection performance and interactivity of the visualization regarding other system parameters. A first test including the laser projector yielded severe challenges as this projection technology has difficulties to project dot grids. We plan to use this visualization technology for a radar like single line visualization techniques. Whereas the regular beamer projection was sufficient to explore graphical styles, a performance demonstration requires a lot more brightness of projection. As the laser projector also comes with critical safety threats to bystanders and even the operator, we also further explore visual and head-up techniques for the already developed visualization techniques. We also plan to implement a hardware control setup that allows the operator to control and manipulate visualization properties, to activate or deactivate the projection and to adjust intensity and resolution during work shifts (see Figure 33). It is used to identify beneficial configurations. The final interface should use hardware controls.

Figure 36: Two different versions of the ground projection visualization that were tested in the Lab demonstrator.

Figure 37: A first version of a separate tablet-based user interface for manipulating the visualization style and mapping mode during work shifts.

4.3 Conclusion and lessons learned

The different visualization technologies have been successfully implemented in the HMI-lab and partly in the real excavator. The HMI-environment is perfectly suited to prototype rough ideas with little implementation effort. Especially the design choices and different variants can be compared and tested here. These early design choices are derived in workshops with specialists from TUD because they can easily abstract the lab setting to the real application since they know about the project context. End-users without experience in such visualization prototype scenarios tend to struggle with the reference of the real working environment. This is possibly due to the limited amount of interactivity and reactivity of the system. The design favourites are then transferred to the real excavator which requires much more implementation effort. With the real machine, tests and demos in real working environments can be performed. Some experts tried out the system without structured experimental setups, but the first impressions have all been positive. The LED-matrix display showed some problems with visibility in bright daylight (especially dark blue colours), which could be mitigated by using different colours. The animation for the height control has been extended to a fine and coarse mode to have a higher resolution for the height difference close to the target height. These design optimizations have already been implemented. The ambient light, which encodes the risk for a collision with a person seems to be very intuitive. The feedback is positive, but the first impressions are without any real working task that demand full attention by the operator. The suitability of the system will

be tested in an experiment in which the operators have to perform a very demanding task. If they still recognize the potential risk, this confirms the functionality of the system. The benefit of the 3d-mapping of the surrounding is not directly understandable for some users. A validation of this system against a state-of-the-art machine control system without mapping function is an effective approach to optimize this technology.

CREA has developed an excavator simulator and especially investigated simulation of the boom forces and possibilities to make the internal load state of the excavator boom visible in real time during the operation. The real time dynamic simulation including interaction with the environment requires balance with the resulting accuracy and simulation period there is to compute the result. The latest Nvidia PhysX5 physics engine was taken in use and its performance as well as the simulation accuracy are better than in previous version 4.1. The first tests have shown that the virtual measurements of the forces are enough accurate, and performance is stable. CREA integrated a virtual LIDAR to excavator. The LIDAR produces a 3D point cloud of the simulated environment. This point cloud information can be overlaid in the Unity visual or streamed separately via IP. In the simulation a virtual camera can be mounted to the machine or somewhere else in the scene, and the view from this camera can be streamed. Based on the tests the performance of the simulation is good and runs in real time. To support testing of the laser projection and spotlight virtual counter parts were developed using decals of the UNITY graphics engine. Both laser projection and the spotlight can be controlled by virtual IO channels, which can be connected for example to CAN messages sent by a controlling system. Tests have shown that decals are very effective and there can be dozens, and the visualization does not require substantially more GPU power.

4.4 Next Steps

The presented implementations will be further improved performance wise and function wise. Performance-wise improvements will also include the implementation of TTCControl control systems. The overall visualization infrastructure and interaction system is the controlling system that will connect all solutions together and enables the handling of the available data inside the cabin. Currently, the system is still under development and first integration steps with individual technology providers is currently taking place. First demonstration activities have been performed so far and more are planned according to the technologies to be integrated in the use case demonstrator. Functionwise, we plan to extend visualization capabilities and their adaptability. This concerns presenting information about hidden objects, visualization and manipulation of reference geometries and manipulation of visualization properties with a dedicated UI. This will be explored and designed in the Lab environment end refined after being implemented into the real machine.

As in the previous use cases, impressions from the tests and demonstrations have been gathered by HdM and presented to vehicle operators from all use cases at various points during WP3 co-design activities to illustrate the project progress and specific technology concepts. For example, impressions of the light bar functionality around the cabin front window have served to visualize and discuss this feature in co-design workshops with vehicle operators across all use cases, since this technology may be applied in the UC1 snow groomer cabin, the virtual UC2 reach stacker cabin (remote control desk) and UC3 excavator cabin. We are planning to arrange demonstrations of this and other UC3 technologies for an excavator operator community that we are currently in contact with (see D3.1/D3.2) to gather more feedback, e.g., on the ideal configuration of the light feedback system.

Regarding the excavator simulator, the next step is to share the latest version with TUD and continue development of the simulation to best support the testing of the new ideas and concepts in the simulated environment. The target is that the simulator is as well integrated with the cabin mockup to present and test project results.

As user testing starts in the second half of the project, design and functional adjustments will be made especially regarding preferred information visualisation techniques and designs as well as required interaction functions to manipulate visualization forms to suit individual preferences, domain-specific requirements across all use-cases and work situations. For such interaction functions we plan to investigate display-based controls, physical controls and gesture controls especially regarding their capability to fit into machine specific control routines.

5 Conclusions

This deliverable provides a summary of all implementations, testing and demonstration activities performed since now within the project. For each of those actions feedback is provided, looking promising already at this early stage. Findings out of the gained experience are used to further improve the development of the methodologies and technologies in WP3, WP4 and WP5. Results will be summarized in D6.3. In conclusion, the testing of different XR technologies and approaches across all three use cases were successful in verifying functionality and providing insights in further functional and design improvement. Several sensor and data processing technologies, XR information presentation approaches including XR feedback and interaction functionalities have been successfully implemented in the Labs and test machines. The HMI-environment is perfectly suited to prototype rough ideas with little implementation effort. Especially the design choices and different variants can be compared and tested here. Initial testing with developers and operators helped to improve understanding of the technologies' potential. Operators were generally enthusiastic about the potential inclusion of haptics once they had gained a better feel for what these technologies enable. The integration of XR environments with human-centred evaluation and design methods has shown great promise for early-stage UX design. Over several development cycles across all use cases, test users provided valuable feedback on innovative approaches for the remote operation concept, although challenges remain, such as the learning curve associated with XR UI elements, particularly with gesture-based interactions. Critical insights could be obtained for example for the precise design of haptic feedback, the importance of high-level sensor calibration for intuitive information presentation in XR and the role of interactivity in XR information presentation. The role of privacy and ethical considerations were considered during the development process and was discussed as data acquisition and impact of our tested XR interactions become more specific as for example shown by the results of the demonstration of the haptic device. The current state of technology implementation already improved functional fidelity and improvements for data availability. This provides the basis for effective user testing in the second half of the project. Evidence will then be used to further improve design, and functional adjustments, especially regarding preferred information visualisation techniques and designs as well as required interaction functions to manipulate XR features to suit individual preferences, domain-specific requirements across all use-cases and work situations.

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ABBREVIATIONS / ACRONYMS

AI	Artificial Intelligence
AR	Augmented Reality
CAN	Control Area Network
CPU	Central Processing Unit
DoF	Degree(s) Of Freedom
IMU	Inertial Measurement Unit
GPU	Graphics Processing Unit
HMD	Head Mounted Display
HMI	Human Machine Interface
LED	Light-Emitting Diode
LIDAR	Light Detection and Ranging
LTS	Long Term Support
OS	Operating System
PC	Personal Computer
RAM	Random Access Memory
RGB	Red, Green and Blue
SDK	Software Development Kit
TAM	Technology Acceptance Model
UC	Use-Case
UI	User Interface
VR	Virtual Reality
WP	Work Package
XR	Extended Reality